

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

BDH2

(3-hydroxybutyrate dehydrogenase 2)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	56898 / Q9BUT1
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Jesse Wiley ¹ , Greg Cary ² , Levon Halabelian ³ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: Full-length BDH2 Baculovirus expression for structure determination

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TRET-AD Target Risk Score: 3.61 (rank #1434, 94.3th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.61 out of 5 (rank #1434, 94.3th percentile). The individual score components include 1.62 of 3 for genetics, and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of BDH2, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. BDH2 is annotated to GO terms from the Metal Binding and Homeostasis and Lipid Metabolism biological domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.611	1434	94.26	1.619	1.992

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of BDH2 is not confidently detected in any cell types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

The role of BDH2 in neurodegeneration and AD is unknown; however, it was discovered as part of a core proteomic module linked with AD pathological and dementia progression in an extended case-control proteomic study(1). Given the minimal literature trail linking BDH2 and neuronal function and neurodegenerative disease, further study would be exceptionally helpful in elucidating the potential roles BDH2 may exert. In order to promote the future study of this topic within the scientific community we are developing a basic target enabling package for BDH2, which includes antibody characterization, protein

production, and bioinformatic characterization of the risk association and cell type expression patterns. We hope that these resources will be useful in fostering scientific investigation by the broader AD community in the future.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The BDH2 gene encodes an NADH-dependent dehydrogenase with an affinity for cyclic compounds (UniProt: Q9BUT1) (2, 3). The small molecule conversations are linked with metabolic function, and coordinate action with LDH2, to sequester free iron, and facilitate its incorporation into heme-like structures (2-6). BDH2 is associated with homeostatic regulation of mitochondrial function, through the regulation of free iron sequestration with LDH2, and other potential mechanisms involved in the regulation of oxidative phosphorylation, and consequently, the potential production of dangerous oxygen free radical toxicants (2, 7). One of the first observations suggesting that BDH2 may have a neurological role came with the observation that treatment of neuron-like N2a cells with MPP+ (a toxic agent that induces midbrain dopaminergic neuronal loss and parkinsonian symptoms) experience a significant decrease in BDH2, and other mitochondrial metabolic genes (7). The decrement in this core gene hub forestalled oxidative phosphorylation in mitochondria, an elevation in glycolysis coupled with lactate production, and a shift to anaerobic metabolism. Unexpectedly, the decrease in oxidative phosphorylation and the associated mitochondrial metabolism regulatory genes were associated with an increase in anti-apoptotic/pro-survival genes (2, 7). This could potentially be reconciled by the recent study observation that decreases in complex I function within the electron transport chain pathway is associated with a decrease in neuronal degeneration in some AD mouse models (8, 9). BDH2's inclusion in this study results from the observation that in ultra-deep proteomic investigations into AD brain function, that BDH2 is part of module 42 (M42), a module that is up regulated in AD and correlates strongly with increases in neuropathology and decreases in clinical cognitive and memory rating scores(1). Intriguingly, another member of the same proteomic module (QPRT (10)) is also involved in NAD-regulation, suggesting a potential mechanistic association between up-regulation of BDH2 and regulation of mitochondrial viability and survival homeostasis. Seemingly paradoxically, in glial blastoma cells, the up-regulation of BDH2 is also associated with an up-regulation of anti-apoptotic genes, potentially suggesting and cell-type specific and biological context specific homeostatic regulation of cellular viability paired with BDH2 regulation (11). Consequently, the mechanism regulating BDH2 and its potential corresponding role in AD pathogenesis are unknown, yet warrant future investigations, that may be promoted by the advancement of this project.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

BDH2_FL_BioN: Full-length BDH2 Baculovirus expression for structure determination. See **Additional Information** for experimental information on protein purification and methods.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of BDH2 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	BDH2
Uniprot ID	Q9BUT1
Region	Full-length

Description	Dehydrogenase/reductase SDR family member 6
Synonyms	DHRS6, SDR15C1
Construct ID	BDH2_FL_BioN (PBC039-E01)
Parental Vector	pFBD-BirA
Tag (N-terminal)	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
Tag (C-terminal)	GGSGHHHHHH
Protein mass (with tag)	30307.57 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	24325
Protein sequence (with tag)	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGMGRLDGKVIILTAAQIGIQAAALAFAREGAKVIATDI NESKLQELEKYPGIQTRVLDVTKKKQIDQFANEVERLDVLFNVAGFVHHGTVLDCEEKDWDFS MNLNVRSMYLMIKAFLPKMLAQKSGNIINMSSVASSVKGVVNRCVYSTTKAAVIGLTKSVAA DFIQQGIRCNCVCPGTVDTPSLQERIQARGNPEEARNDFLKRQKTGRFATAEEIAMLCVYLAS DESAYVTGNPVIIDGGWSLGGSGHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
SEC (step 2): BDH2_FL_BioN	
IEC (step 3): BDH2_FL_BioN	

Intact Mass Deconvolution:	
Observed Mass:	30445.34 Da
Protein yield:	6 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)
Expression Medium	I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre
Transformation and storage	The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.
Expression	For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Wash Buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 5 mM imidazole 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole. 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 150 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. IEC buffer: 20 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 210mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 6. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (2 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 90W output power) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (1 hour, 38400xg, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add the cleared lysate onto (1ml/L) Talon Metal Affinity Resin (Cat# 635504 Clontech) in a 250 mL canonical tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hour in a cold room. 4. Transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Wash column with 2CV of wash buffer.

	7. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.
Purification step 3: Ion exchange chromatography (IEX)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Source Q ion exchange chromatography. 2. Elute with concentration gradient of 20 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP (buffer B). 3. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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